

Protocol S1

S1.1. G2F-E “empty” datasets

To improve the “empty” G2F-E time series, first we need to find the optimal option among NSRDB, DayMet, and NWS for gaps imputation. For that purpose, if there are multiple options for variable m (e.g. T is available in all NSRDB, DayMet, and NWS options), $RMSE$ statistic is calculated between all “complete” G2F-E- m datasets and each of the NSRDB- m , DayMet- m , and NWS- m options. Then the kernel density of pairwise calculated $RMSE$ (Bojanowski et al., 2014) of data sources has been computed to find the best consistent option with G2F-E- m . The consistency criterion for each variable is calculated as follows:

$$RMSE_{m,option} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_{obs,G2F_i} - \hat{y}_{obs,option_i})^2} \quad (1)$$

where, $y_{obs,G2F_i}$ is the observed value of variable m in “complete” G2F-E- m dataset on day i , $\hat{y}_{obs,option_i}$ is the observed value of variable m in other options (NSRDB, DayMet, and NWS) on day i , and N is the number of recorded days for the variable m in the whole “complete” G2F-E- m dataset.

The best-fitted option with the G2F-E- m dataset is used to replace the “empty” time series and then, the reconstructed fulfilled-gaps time series is transferred to the final improved G2F-E database.

S1.2. G2F-E “incomplete” datasets

For infilling missing records in climate time series, several techniques like simple interpolation and linear regression have been proposed (Arriagada et al., 2021). However, these methods perform poorly in case of existing several sequencing data gaps with low number of observations in time series (Bojanowski et al., 2014). Thus, to fill the gaps of the “incomplete”

G2F-E datasets, we designed DNNs between observed G2F-E- m ($y_{obs,G2F}$) and previously proposed climate database options ($\hat{y}_{obs,option}$) for missing data ($y_{miss,G2F}$) fulfillment for each variable m at each G2F experimental trial. In addition, to guarantee the data size is enough for DNN simulation, the “incomplete” datasets with missing records more than 25% of the total are treated as “empty” time series to be imputed (as described in section S1.1).

Here, we explain the improvement section of the pipeline to apply DNN in “incomplete” G2F-E datasets to predict the NaN ($y_{miss,G2F}$) values which are as follows (Figure 2 in Sarzaeim et al., accepted):

- **Data Acquisition:** The first step in DNN application is to select the appropriate input data which the DNN model will be built between. Here, the “incomplete” G2F-E- m time series and associated values from other available options (NSRDB, DayMet, and NWS) at each single experiment location are integrated as inputs. Then, the *RMSE* statistic is calculated between “incomplete” G2F experiments and each of the options. The option with minimum *RMSE* value is selected to be fed into the DNN along with G2F-E- m dataset as inputs. The *RMSE* is calculated as follow:

$$RMSE_{Exp,option} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M (y_{obs,G2F_i} - \hat{y}_{obs,option_i})^2} \quad (2)$$

where, $y_{obs,G2F_i}$ is the observed value of variable m in the “incomplete” G2F-E- m at the experimental field *Exp* on day i , $\hat{y}_{obs,option_i}$ is the observed value of variable m in other options at the experimental field *Exp* on day i , and M is the number of recorded days with observed value for variable m in the “incomplete” G2F-E- m dataset at the experimental field *Exp*.

- **Data Cleaning and Identifying:** The goal is to simulate the $y_{miss,G2F_i}$ in G2F-E- m time series at each experiment location from building the DNN between $y_{obs,G2F_i}$ and $\hat{y}_{obs,option_i}$. Since the

minimum, average, and maximum time series of variable m are required for GxE simulation, these time series are calculated from $y_{obs,G2F_i}$ and $\hat{y}_{obs,option_i}$ for variable m and embedded in database (these three time series have been considered for T , DP , RH and SR , while for WS and WD the average values and for R the accumulated value have been accounted). Next, the “Select Best” function of Python has been employed to detect the best correlated feature among minimum, average, and maximum of the selected option to estimate the gaps available in the each of minimum, average, and maximum G2F-E- m time series for each experiment. Then, the selected feature along with the $y_{obs,G2F_i}$ are scaled using Min-Max scaling approach by “MinMaxScaler” function in Python to be prepared as inputs to the DNN model.

- Training, Testing, Building, and Validation the Model: The scaled input datasets are split into two groups. We assigned 60% of input set to train the model and 40% to test that. A four-layer, fully connected perceptron DNN model is built between the daily minimum, average, and maximum measurements for variable m (T , DP , RH , and SR) in “incomplete” G2F-E- m time series and the selected feature from the option (NSRDB, DayMet, and NWS) at each G2F experiment location. The number of nodes assigned to the first hidden layer, the second hidden layer, and the output layer are 15, 10, and 1, respectively. For variable SR note that always daily $SR_{min} = 0$, thus we create DNN to predict missing daily SR_{mean} and SR_{max} . Regarding R , one DNN is designed to simulate accumulated daily rainfall (R_{acc}). For each WS and WD also one DNN is created to predict the gaps in WS_{mean} and WD_{mean} time series, respectively. The $\min(MSE)$ has been selected as a cost function and the training will be terminated after 10,000 epochs. The MSE function is computed to evaluate the model’s predictability performance in test population:

$$MSE_{test} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (y_{obs_t} - \hat{y}_{sim_t})^2 \quad (3)$$

where, y_{obs_t} = the observed value of record t in test set, \hat{y}_{sim_t} = the simulated value of record t in test set, and T = the total number of records in test set.

Rectified linear unit has been set as activation function. Cui et al. (2020) mentioned that rectified linear unit is capable to transfer the intense information through multiple layers. The ‘‘Adam’’ optimization algorithm has been used to optimize the built model in training step, which is computationally effective and well-suited for large data (Cui et al., 2020). For input dataset preprocessing and building the DNNs purposes in this study, we have employed user-friendly, open-source, and easy-deployable ‘‘sklearn’’, ‘‘tensorflow’’, and ‘‘keras’’ libraries of Python (Apolo-Apolo et al., 2020).

- **Model Deployment:** In last step of G2F-E- m improvement pipeline, the $y_{miss,G2F}$ in the time series which have been removed in ‘‘Data Cleaning and Identifying’’ step, are fed into the built best-fitted model as new model input to simulate the missing values in m_{min} , m_{mean} , m_{max} time series. After missing values simulation, the entire improved G2F-E- m datasets are transferred to the final improved G2F-E database.

References

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